

Deliverable D1.8

Project Title:	Building data bridges between biological and medical infrastructures in Europe	
Project Acronym:	BioMedBridges	
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	Research Infrastructures, FP7 Capacities Specific Programme; [INFRA-2011-2.3.2.] "Implementation of common solutions for a cluster of ESFRI infrastructures in the field of "Life sciences"	
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WP No.	1	
Lead Beneficiary:	1: EMBL	
WP Title	Management	
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WP leader:	Janet Thornton	1: EMBL
Contributing partner(s):	n/a	

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Contents

1	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
2	PROJECT OBJECTIVES	3
3	DETAILED REPORT ON THE DELIVERABLE	4
3.1	Introduction to the project	4
3.2	Ethical Governance Framework, Audit, Templates and Legal Assessment Tool	4
3.3	Definitions of relevant terms	6
3.4	Risk of (re-)identification	7
3.5	Overall assessment of the ethics provision for the BioMedBridges project.....	8
4	DELIVERY AND SCHEDULE	8
5	ADJUSTMENTS MADE	8
6	ATTACHMENTS	9
7	BACKGROUND INFORMATION	9

1 Executive summary

The BioMedBridges project better enables researchers to access a wide range of data across different disciplines and allows re-analysis of datasets, some of which will have been generated through rare, expensive or unrepeatabe investigations, thereby ensuring maximum utility of these datasets and facilitating new discoveries in health research. However, the sharing of data generated through the use of human material brings about ethical challenges concerning the protection of research participant privacy and confidentiality. To address this, a comprehensive ethical governance structure was put in place, including an Ethical Governance Committee consisting of external experts that advises the project's Executive Steering Committee, and an Ethical Governance Framework document. In addition, to ensure compliance with the framework, the project is assisted by an Independent External Ethics Adviser. This report is the final report of the External Ethics Adviser.

The overall assessment of the IEEA is that the ethical governance structure and framework, such as the relevant committees, EGF, audit, templates and tool, have worked well.

2 Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Manage the BioMedBridges project from Year 1-4		x
2	Organise the management meetings for all the project including: the Annual General Meeting for all partners; the Executive Steering Committee meetings (up to twice per annum) and the regular meetings of the Technical Coordination Committee (up to 3 times per annum)		x

3	Organise the Scientific Advisory Committee and their annual meeting, including reporting back to all partners		x
4	Provide good communication between all partners, through a professional web site		x
5	Ensure timely and appropriate reporting to the commission and completion of deliverables in all Work Packages		x
6	Develop metrics to assess the progress of the grant and its impact on the BMS community		x
7	Develop with all partners a plan for sustainability of the infrastructure built during the project, following completion of the grant		x
8	Ensure that ethics issues are addressed	x	

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Introduction to the project

The BioMedBridges project aimed to better enable researchers to access a wide range of data to facilitate new discoveries in health research and allowed re-analysis of datasets, some of which were generated through rare, expensive or unrepeatable investigations, thereby ensuring maximum utility of these datasets. Although the project did not involve the generation of new data, the sharing of data brought its own ethical challenges.

3.2 Ethical Governance Framework, Audit, Templates and Legal Assessment Tool

In order for the different project entities to operate in unison and focus on relevant ethical issues, an Ethical Governance Framework (EGF) was drafted in consultation with representatives from the relevant Research Infrastructures

(RIs). The Framework set out policies for the project relating to ethical and regulatory issues with the aim to ensure data supplied into the project was appropriate and could be made accessible to other researchers.

The EGF made it clear that data providers were responsible for ensuring that any data they made available could be shared in compliance with national and international regulations, research participant consent, and ethics committee conditions of approval, where appropriate. Appropriate consent from research participants and/or approval from regulatory bodies should also have been sought by the data providers to trans-border/international access and linking data or types of data that were not linked before, where appropriate. Obligations regarding feedback of research findings were highlighted, but the EGF cautioned against the direct feeding back of research results to research participants where those results had not been validated to a diagnostic standard. It also commented that open commitments to continuously re-evaluate data ad infinitum in order to feedback findings were not practical or sustainable.

The project's IEEA, Carol Smee, and the Project Manager, Stephanie Suhr, carried out a review of compliance with the Ethical Governance Framework across all work packages (WPs). Preliminary analysis of the data showed that only one WP, WP8, had data for which a BioMedBridges Data Provider Form¹ would need to be completed, and this WP had raised specific issues regarding how sharing of data might be achieved and yet still ensure compliance with the requirements of the Framework. One dataset from Finland was considered as a use case, and the report on this use case was made available to the funders in the document 'Ethical Compliance Audit Results' (<https://zenodo.org/record/13769>) appended to the IEAA Report 2014.

In order to assist data providers and other researchers outside the project in recruiting future research participants, a template information sheet and consent form were produced by the project and published

¹ This form must be completed by all parties providing data, where there are underlying restrictions on use imposed by consent requirements, ethics committee approvals, national regulations or any other agreements within the BioMedBridges project.

(<http://www.biomedbridges.eu/deliverables/52-0>) The templates drew upon guidance from a variety of sources, including UK National Research Ethics Service (NRES) and EU biobank consent templates, and may be used by anyone in the initial stages of designing a study. The templates are deemed suitable for use throughout the EU.

To further assist researchers, the project developed a Legal Assessment Tool (LAT)^{2,3} to support data and sample providers and present the regulatory requirements for sharing sensitive data and/or samples. The LAT achieves this by guiding the user through a structured query, web-based graphical user interface. At the end of the query process, regulatory requirements, related information, solutions for fulfilling requirements and related templates are provided.

The EGF made reference to the use of data obtained via animal experimentation, and stated that such data could only be used in the project if the research undertaken to generate it complied with the requirements of national and EU regulations, and was carried out under appropriate licences or with other appropriate authority as relevant. It was agreed that if data generators worked within these requirements, this would ensure that due regard had been given to animal care and welfare.

3.3 Definitions of relevant terms

During the drafting of the EGF, there was discussion concerning **ownership versus custodianship of data**. It was determined that the term ownership implied holding the legal title and full property rights to one or more specific items of data, which would in turn imply that the 'owner' had the right or possibility, for example, to sell that data onwards or to destroy it - neither of which is the case. The study participant, the researcher, and the IT/data manager all have different rights and responsibilities that cannot usefully be described as 'ownership'. In contrast, custodians have legal rights and

² Sariyar M, Schluender I, Smee C, Suhr S. Sharing and Reuse of Sensitive Data and Samples: Supporting Researchers in Identifying Ethical and Legal Requirements. *Biopreservation and Biobanking*. 2015;Vol.13;No.4:263-270

³ <http://www.biomedbridges.eu/deliverables/52-0>

responsibilities which are transferable from one custodian to another so, consequently, this was determined to be the more suitable term.

There was some discussion on how **anonymisation** might be defined in the project. Although there is no internationally recognised definition and many terms abound, such as de-identified, linked anonymised, coded, pseudonymised, it was important to define the terms used in the project documentation so that all RIs understood what was meant by each term. It was decided⁴ that the term ‘anonymisation’ would be used to describe any data where identifiable information was not available to the researchers using the data. This term describes fully or unlinked anonymised data, but also linked, coded or pseudonymised data where the linkage key (code or cipher) is not held by, nor accessible to, the researchers/research establishment. Unlinked anonymised data contain no information that could reasonably allow anyone to identify the individuals to whom they relate, whereas linked anonymised (or coded or pseudonymised) data are anonymous to the researchers but contain information or codes that would allow others, such as a patient’s clinician, to link them back to individuals. The EGF was revised to include the agreed definition.

The differences across countries in the EU regarding the definition of **personal data** were also considered. In some EU jurisdictions, personal data may be used to describe human biosamples since the information contained in the DNA within a biosample is unique to an individual and may be used to identify them. However, it was agreed that in BioMedBridges documentation, the term ‘personal data’ would refer to data which may be used to identify a research participant, such as name, address, National Insurance number, full postcode, and would not be applied to DNA sequence data.

3.4 Risk of (re-)identification

Although the data linked to in the project were anonymised, and no identifiable data would be shared, some types of data held about a research participant could be unique - such as a person’s whole genome sequence – and, if linked

⁴ Based on the recommendation by the Independent External Ethics Adviser and Irene Schluender, legal expert in WP5, TMF, Germany

to other sources of data containing identifiable information, then the research participant may be identified. The project acknowledged this risk, but could only ensure that datasets within its control were anonymised, and suggested that anyone combining datasets should consider any increased risk of identification that may arise as more and more pieces of information about an individual were brought together. Although it could be possible to inform research participants during the consent process of the risk of identifiability, it would be difficult for researchers or clinicians seeking consent to foresee all uses to which research data may be put in the future, and to explain how datasets may be combined. It was decided, therefore, that research participants should be informed that although risk of identification could be considered to be minimal, true risks may be unknown and could not be forecast. Data providers were informed through the EGF that if they had any doubt as to whether combining datasets could proceed, or whether consent provisions allowed for the combination of datasets, the opinion of a relevant ethics committee or national authority should be sought.

3.5 Overall assessment of the ethics provision for the BioMedBridges project

The IEEA determines that the ethical governance structure and framework, such as the relevant committees, EGF, audit, templates and tool, have worked well, defined difficult concepts and terminology, brought agreement and produced outputs which can be used to inform future ethics policies at EU Research Infrastructures.

4 Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

5 Adjustments made

No adjustments were made.

6 Attachments

ANNEX 1. BioMedBridges Ethical Governance Framework, version 1.2
(updated version October 2014)

(<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11952>)

ANNEX 2. Template Adult Research Participant Information Sheet and
Consent Form

(http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/documents/deliverables/bmb_pis_and_consent_form_adult_v2_final.docx)

ANNEX 3. Template Child Research Participant Information Sheet and
Consent Form

(http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/documents/deliverables/bmb_pis_and_assent_form_child_v1_110714.docx)

ANNEX 4. Progress of compliance with the requirements of the Ethics
Review Report (<https://zenodo.org/record/13769>)

7 Background information

This deliverable relates to WP1; background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of work (DOW) is included below.

WP1 Title: Management
Lead: Janet Thornton, EMBL
Participants: all

The objectives of WP1 are the management of the BioMedBridges project, including organization of the management meetings such as the Annual General Meeting for all partners, the Executive Steering Committee meetings (up to twice per annum) and the regular meetings of the Technical Coordination Committee (up to 3 times per annum), and the meetings of the Scientific Advisory Committee, including reporting back to all partners. Among the tasks is also the provision of tools to ensure good communication between all partners, timely and appropriate reporting to the Commission and completion of deliverables in all Work Packages, development of metrics to assess the progress of the grant and its impact on the BMS community, the development of a plan for sustainability of the infrastructure built during the project and ensuring that any ethics issues that arise are addressed

appropriately.						
Work package number	WP 1	Start date or starting event:				month 1
Work package title	Management					
Activity Type	MGT					
Participant number	1: EMBL	2: UOXF	3: KI	4: STFC	11: HMGU	13: VUMC
Person-months per participant	48	0	1	1	1	1
<p>Objectives</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To manage the BioMedBridges project from Year 1-4 2. To organise the management meetings for all the project including: the Annual General Meeting for all partners; the Executive Steering Committee meetings (up to twice per annum) and the regular meetings of the Technical Coordination Committee (up to 3 times per annum) 3. To organise the Scientific Advisory Committee and their annual meeting, including reporting back to all partners 4. To provide good communication between all partners, through a professional web site 5. To ensure timely and appropriate reporting to the commission and completion of deliverables in all Work Packages 6. To develop metrics to assess the progress of the grant and its impact on the BMS community 7. To develop with all partners a plan for sustainability of the infrastructure built during the project, following completion of the grant 8. To ensure that ethics issues are addressed 						
<p>Description of work and role of participants</p> <p>The project will be coordinated by Professor Janet Thornton at EMBL-EBI. The management structure will consist of an Executive Steering Committee, made up of the coordinators of the individual ESFRI BMS projects, and a Technical Coordination Committee, consisting of the Chairs and Co-chairs of the work packages. Janet Thornton will chair both committees. The Technical Coordination Committee will report to the Coordinator and Executive Steering</p>						

Committee on a regular basis.

The tasks for this WP are as follows:

Task 1: Overall Coordination of the project The coordinator of BioMedBridges has full responsibility for managing this project and achieving its objectives, including infrastructure construction, project reporting and impact assessment and finance. The coordinator will be supported by a full time project manager, whose role will be to provide day-to-day support and implementation of all management and organisational tasks, including taking charge of accounting for all financial aspects of the project. The project manager will be responsible for the content management of the web site.

An Executive Steering Committee, consisting of all the coordinators of the 10 BMS Infrastructures, which are contributing to this grant. This committee, which is chaired by the BioMedBridges coordinator (who also coordinates the ELIXIR infrastructure), will play a strategic role in the management of the project and be responsible for decisions on the financial management. They will measure progress against the specific objectives, milestones and deliverables of each work package, developing metrics to measure the impact of the work. They will also ensure good coordination with the members of their own the infrastructure. They will oversee the consolidation of the data-infrastructure needs of the different projects, and develop a joint policy on these issues. They will monitor the sustainability of the components of the infrastructure being developed and develop a plan for support following the completion of this grant. The Executive Board will meet twice in the first year: a kick-off meeting and an ordinary Board meeting. In subsequent years, there would be annual meetings, as well as conference calls every two to three months. It is anticipated that the meetings would be held in connection with the Annual General Meetings where possible.

The Technical Coordination Committee will comprise the coordinator of the grant and scientists in charge of different aspects of the construction work with responsibility for coordinating one work package (ie the chairs and co-chairs of the different construction Work Packages 1 - 5). The use case chairs will join this group as appropriate, during the tenure of their use case. This committee will therefore include technical experts taken from each infrastructure. This Committee has the responsibility to assess and report to the Executive Steering Committee on the progress of the work packages and to identify and prioritise future tasks for the following year. The chair for this committee will be the coordinator of the project. The Technical Coordination Committee will focus on the day-to-day and technical issues involved in achieving the planned deliverables and constructing the infrastructure. The Technical Coordination Committee will meet up to twice per year, in addition to the Annual General Meetings, and have monthly conference calls to deal with routine issues and resolve any urgent problems which may arise. The chairs and co-chairs of each Work Package will manage their own WP, ensuring good communication both

within the WP and with the rest of this project, through this committee. This is described in more detail in the management section 2.1 below.

Task 2: Organisation of Management Meetings

The whole consortium will meet once a year at the Annual General Meetings. This meeting will involve all the partners and those employed and working on the grant. Presentations will be made on progress on each work package and the use cases described. In the first year there will be an additional meeting at the start of the grant, to ensure good coordination from the beginning. The AGMs would also be the main opportunity for the Executive Board and the Technical coordination Committee to meet and take joint decisions on the direction of the project, and for the advisory bodies (see below) to learn about the project and the progress being made, as well as providing strategic advice. The last AGM will be an open meeting, in part to provide outreach to all the members of each infrastructure, and also to ensure good uptake and exploitation of the deliverables of BioMedBridges. This meeting will be coordinated by WP2.

Task 3: Organisation of Scientific Advisory Board

The project will have two advisory bodies. We will construct a Scientific Advisory Board, which will comprise a small number of experts in the biological and biomedical life science infrastructure area. This will include world class biologists, IT experts, ethical and legal experts. In addition, representatives of the large e-infrastructures will be invited to form a Technology Watch e-Advisory Task Force, to keep the project informed on developments in this field and in general guarantee a close association between the ICT e-infrastructures and this project. The e-Advisory Task Force will form the Technology Watch Work Package (WP11), and consequently play a more integral part in the project than a conventional advisory board. It is anticipated that both advisory bodies would meet in connection with the Annual General Meetings.

Task 4: Provision of a professional web site

As well as providing the project with a public face, the project web site is also an important management tool. For this reason, the web site has been included in this work package, and will be based at EMBL-EBI, co-located with the coordinator and project manager. The internal/restricted part of the web site will be used both as a workplace and as a repository of documents. The task here is to provide the technical infrastructure for the website, whose contents will be controlled by the project manager.

Task 5: Reporting on the Project to Commission

The project coordinator will be responsible for reporting to the commission, with

help from the project manager. Reports from each work package will be delivered by the chair of that work package to the project coordinator, who will then combine these reports to deliver a coordinated report.

Task 6: Developing and monitoring progress and impact

The management bodies will develop procedures and metrics at the beginning of the grant to measure the progress of the grant and its impact on the biological and medical research communities. These metrics will be reported annually. All the partners involved in this WP will have responsibility for this task.

Task 7: Developing Sustainability Plan

During the course of the project the executive steering committee will monitor the sustainability of the infrastructure under construction. All the partners involved in this WP will have responsibility for this task. In the last year of the project the executive steering Committee will report on the long term sustainability of each component delivered.

Task 8: Establish an Ethical Governance Committee

The Ethical Governance Committee will:

- provide an ethics management report to each meeting of BioMedBridges Executive Steering Committee
- Analyse the requirements from the Ethics Review Report
- Review the draft Ethical Governance Framework document
- Monitor the compliance of the project beneficiaries with the Ethical Governance Framework
- Prepare new versions of the Ethical Governance Framework for approval by the Executive Steering Committee
- Support the External Independent Ethics Advisor in the preparation of Progress of Compliance with Ethics Requirements Reports.

Subcontracting for Audit Certificates: EMBL (Partner 1), STFC (Partner 4), UDUS (Partner 5), TUM-MED (Partner 7), TMF (Partner 10), HMGU (Partner 11), VUMC (Partner 13), UH (Partner 16).

Deliverables

No.	Name	Due month
D1.1	Website	12

D1.2	Devise metrics to measure progress and impact of construction	12
D1.3	1 st Periodic Report	18
D1.4	2 nd Periodic Report	36
D1.5	Final Report & Sustainability Plan	48
D1.6	ED1: The Ethical Governance Framework for BioMedBridges	18
D1.7	ED2: Progress of compliance with requirements of the Ethics Review Report	36
D1.8	ED3: External Independent Ethics Advisors Report	48